

HUMILITY AND NOBILITY – LANDMARKS OF DEIFICATION IN THE SPIRITUAL THINKING OF SAINT PAISIOS THE AGHIORITE

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ABSTRACT: Humility and nobility – landmarks of deification in the spiritual thinking of Saint Paisios the Aghiorite.

We will not be wrong in stating that the 20th century was, paradoxically, a time of intensified research into divine grace upon humanity, in a way perhaps more visible than in other historical eras. Thus, the apostolic word is fulfilled: “Where sin increased, grace did much more abound” (*Romans* 5, 20). This observation is based on the impressive number of saints whose faith has produced in this age of suffering and death, as a living response to the darkness of the world, since “The light shines in the darkness, and the darkness has not comprehended it” (*John* 1, 5).

In what follows, we will focus on the spiritual teaching of Saint Paisios the Aghiorite, regarding the prerequisites for an authentic and effective conversation between man and God. He himself stood out as a living example of a spiritual “transmitter”, a relay between heaven and earth, capable of capturing and retransmitting divine grace through his ascetic life and his discerning word.

Keywords: *humility, spiritual nobility, spirituality, deification, love*

1. The Face of Humility in the Spiritual Thought of Saint Paisios the Aghiorite

For the dialogue with God to be authentic and fruitful, it is essential to identify the correct “frequency” of communication. Like a transmission system, if the frequencies are incompatible, communication turns into a monologue or a “dialogue of the deaf”. In the relationship with God,

dysfunction can only be on the part of man, since God, in His boundless love, has offered countless proofs of goodwill and desire for communion, culminating in the incarnation of His Son, who took on the form of man to unite Himself ontologically with humanity.

Once the cause of the blockage – pride – has been identified, the remedy remains to be clarified. Here too, Saint Paisios the Aghiorite offers a clear solution, expressed in his characteristic, profound and plastic style: “Humility opens the gate of heaven and the mysteries of God are revealed to the humble.”¹

This contemporary apophthegm leads us to understand that pride is the main obstacle to dialogue with God. Although man has a vital need for communion with God – more than air – communication often remains suspended due to the refusal to give up self, arrogance, and self-sufficiency. Spiritual experience shows that man, paradoxically, would like God to adapt to the “frequency” of his pride, to respect his “right” to be proud. Such a claim, however, is evidence of a profound misunderstanding of spiritual realities, a form of spiritual blindness and alienation from the logic of grace.

The defining property of pride consists in the fact that the proud man constantly perceives himself superior to the one in front of him, despising both his gestures and his words. In such a setting, dialogue between two proud individuals becomes impossible, as each will attempt to dominate the other, either through submission or – in the event of failure – by rendering the other irrelevant as an interlocutor. Pride does not allow communion but generates conflict and isolation.

In contrast, humility illuminates the soul and protects it from spiritual obstacles, offering it stability and progress in the spiritual life. Where there is humility, there is also spiritual growth. The more deeply a person humbles himself, the more grace he receives from God and moves forward with greater steadfastness. Humility is a mysterious force, often undervalued, although it has immense transforming power. Those who have found the path of humble contemplation move forward in the spiritual life without effort, because the devil cannot overthrow a soul in which humility is at work. The humble one does not fall, because he

1 Sfântul PAISIE AGHIORITUL, *Mica Filocalie*, trad. Victor Manolache, Ed. Egu-menița și Ed. Cartea Ortodoxă, Galați, 2009, p. 165.

walks with realism and balance on the earth.² Authentic humility does not lead to despair, but to hope, since the humble person puts his trust in God's mercy.³

The Psalmist David testifies: "In our humility the Lord remembered us" (*Psalms* 135, 23), emphasizing that humility not only makes us obedient to God, but even in our silence, God takes care of us.

Saint Silouan the Athonite affirms that perfect humility is Christ Himself, and Saint Paisios the Athonite reinforces this teaching, saying: "Where there is humility, pride disappears; where there is Christ, the devil departs. Humility is what makes the devil limp; it is the greatest shock for him. Humility fights the passions and the devil and completes the work of the powerless."⁴ Moreover, "He who prays with humility and with the fear of God has the grace of God with him."⁵

All these testimonies converge to the conclusion that humility is indispensable for the spiritual growth of man. Saint Paisios often warned, with fatherly care, about the serious consequences of abandoning humility: "The proud is separated from God, because pride is an evil conductor; it is an insulator that does not let the Grace of God pass through and separates us from God."⁶ Thus, humility is not only a virtue, but an essential condition for communion with God and for preserving grace in the soul.

2. Spiritual nobility – condition of authentic communication with God and sign of deified humanity

One of the most widespread diseases of the contemporary world is the lack of nobility. In the absence of this virtue, excess selfishness generates suffering, affecting both the individual's spiritual balance and interpersonal relationships. Nobility, in its profound dimension, is not exclusively the attribute of man or God, but the result of a synergy between the human will and divine energy, implying the assumption of sacrifice, self-denial and renunciation of selfishness.

2 Sfântul PAISIE AGHIORITUL, „Patimi și virtuți”, în col.: *Cuvinte duhovnicești*, vol. V, Ed. Evanghelismos, București, 2007, pp. 288-289.

3 Sfântul PAISIE AGHIORITUL, „Patimi și virtuți”, p. 289.

4 Sfântul PAISIE AGHIORITUL, „Patimi și virtuți”, p. 163.

5 Sfântul PAISIE AGHIORITUL, „Patimi și virtuți”, p. 164.

6 Sfântul PAISIE AGHIORITUL, „Patimi și virtuți”, p. 53.

The supreme model of nobility remains the Savior Jesus Christ, who sacrificed Himself out of love for man. Unlike us, He did not have to defeat His own selfishness, but assumed with dignity the ingratitude, hatred, and contempt of those for whom He offered His life. His nobility confronted human insensitivity, and because it was His own – He being Nobility incarnate – He acted without reserve and without regret. Spiritual nobility is defined by two apparently contradictory features: it attracts with its beauty and repels with its perfect humility, to which few can rise. It is the challenge of giving up personal comfort, even one's own life, for the sake of the other, to live through him, through the piece of life offered to him. In this sense, the evangelical word remains normative: "Whoever loves his life will lose it, and whoever loses his life for my sake will find it." (*Matthew* 10, 39)

The painful observation of the first generation of Christians, expressed by the Holy Apostle and Evangelist John – "the world lies in the power of the evil one" (*1 John* 5, 19) – remains valid to this day, like a chronic illness. Two defining symptoms of this state attract attention: the paralyzing inertia of the world and the despotic rule of the evil one. The world, understood as a topos and a global entity with impersonal tendencies, stagnates in its egotism, offering only the appearance of a satisfying life. To lie down means, after all, to be on the edge of the abyss of death.

In the Old Testament, this agonizing state is illustrated as a trophy of the victory of evil over the righteous man: "Does he not lie down? He will not rise again!" (*Psalms* 40, 8) The prophet Jeremiah describes the collapse of the unbelieving woman, the height of fecundity⁷ in sin, who has reached impotence (*Jeremiah* 15, 9), thus prefiguring Christ's victory over sin and death. Holofernes, the leader of the Assyrian army, is shown fallen, his head cut off (*Book of Judith* 14, 18), a symbol of the ephemerality of the success of evil in contrast to the constancy of good.

In the New Testament, lying down is explicitly mentioned in three episodes: the servant of the centurion Cornelius (*Matthew* 8, 6), the Jewish people enslaved by unbelief (*Galatians* 4:24), and the entire world, weakened by vitality (*1 John* 5, 19). These images reflect the fallen state

7 Her seven children may signify the seven arms of the capital passions, offspring or ramifications into new hypostases of the soul's death.

of humanity, similar to that of the unfortunate man who fell among robbers⁸, left “almost dead.” (*Luke* 10, 30)⁹

Faced with this generalized suffering, Saint Paisios the Athonite (1924–1994) dedicated himself to comforting and healing wounded souls, through prayer, word, and deed. A true genius of Orthodox spirituality, he observed that the fundamental problem of community and personal life is the almost total absence of the virtue of nobility. Spiritual nobility, says Saint Paisius, is “spiritual superiority, it is sacrifice”¹⁰ – the call of man to the unity of nature and to the fulfillment of the Law of merciful love.¹¹

Nobility is a divine-human state, a way of relating to the world that puts the will of God and the spiritual good of one’s neighbor in the foreground. In its working form, nobility is crowned with the halo of holiness, exceeding the boundaries of reciprocity. It makes man like God in goodness, generosity and humility. In this sense, the monk Nicholas Steinhart of Rohia states: “Christ God is a nobleman, a gentleman, a boyar”.¹² In his

8 Robbers of lust and passions, most often. We suggest this interpretation, in accordance with the patristic tradition, taking into account the “descent” mentioned in the parable of the Good Samaritan, in which the fallen one “went down from Jerusalem to Jericho” (from the Temple of God located on Mount Zion to the city of Jericho, the oldest, at least in the region of Palestine, outdated in the experimentation of many generations of the various modes of human moral collapse.

9 Another, brighter translation prefers the phrase “barely alive”.

10 Sfântul PAISIE AGHIORITUL, „Patimi și virtuți”, p. 245.

11 Within the Roman Catholic tradition, there is a congregation called the Sons of Merciful Love, founded in Rome on August 15, 1951, with the declared purpose of confessing Merciful Love. This expression, deeply rooted in the Christian vocabulary since the apostolic era, brings together the two dimensions of divine love: transfigured eros and active mercy, both manifestations of God’s love for man. The earthly life of the Savior Jesus Christ remains the standard of this vocation of the sons of the heavenly Father, being the supreme expression of merciful love incarnate. The evangelical exhortations are clear and revealing: “Be merciful, just as your Father is merciful.” (*Luke* 6:36) “I desire mercy, not sacrifice.” (*Hosea* 6, 6; cf. *Matthew* 9, 13; 12, 7) “You shall love the Lord your God with all your heart, with all your soul, with all your mind, and with all your strength. This is the first commandment. And the second is this: You shall love your neighbor as yourself. There is no other commandment greater than these” (*Mark* 12, 30–31). These verses constitute the foundation of a Christian anthropology centered on merciful love, in which man is called to reflect, actively and responsibly, the love of God in his relationship with his fellow men. Thus, divine eros and mercy are not abstract concepts, but lived realities, which must be concretely assumed in the personal and community life of the believer.

12 Nicolae STEINHARDT, *Jurnalul fericii*, Ed. Dacia, Cluj-Napoca, 1999, p. 146.

vision, the Lord's "boyarism" is expressed through discretion¹³, courage¹⁴, trust in people¹⁵, a predisposition for forgiveness¹⁶, constant availability for help¹⁷, selfless kindness¹⁸, attentiveness, constant politeness¹⁹, indiscriminate love²⁰, abundant generosity²¹, condemnation of sin²², awareness of noble origin²³, and immunity to contagious evil.²⁴

13 Nicolae STEINHARDT, *Jurnalul fericirii*, p. 103. Discretion as a humble attitude, not seeking vain glory.

14 Nicolae STEINHARDT, *Jurnalul fericirii*, p. 103. Courage takes different forms: giving oneself up, upholding the Truth at any risk.

15 Nicolae STEINHARDT, *Jurnalul fericirii*, p. 104. Trust in man in the sense of a fair appreciation of the value of the human being and of unshakable confidence in the potential for return and progress on the path of goodness. Non-judgment and perfect friendship are expressions of noble love, the love that "covers a multitude of sins" (1 Peter 4, 8).

16 Nicolae STEINHARDT, *Jurnalul fericirii*, p. 103. What is highlighted here is forgiveness easily and fully, unlike the common attitude of the "trickster" who "never forgives, or if he relents (again to forgive), he does it with difficulty, reluctantly, with a grumble."

17 Nicolae STEINHARDT, *Jurnalul fericirii*, p. 103. There is an inner, finite willingness to help, eager to help, filled with pity.

18 Nicolae STEINHARDT, *Jurnalul fericirii*, p. 104. His goodwill is both boundless and disinterested: He shows it with the same enthusiasm "towards the afflicted from whom you cannot derive any benefit (the sick, foreigners, prisoners)."

19 Nicolae, STEINHARDT, *Jurnalul fericirii*, p. 104. It is about politeness that maternally credits the change for the better in man, characterized by "the lack of insult or contempt for the sinner", united with compassionate love.

20 Nicolae STEINHARDT, *Jurnalul fericirii*, p. 104. Divine nobility is overwhelmed by the absence of preliminary, additional conditions placed on sinners. Although it is firm about sin, it does not hate the sinner.

21 Nicolae STEINHARDT, *Jurnalul fericirii*, p. 104. The All-Merciful Generosity seems exaggerated, but in this one glimpses its nobility and purity, in the giving "more than it should be, boyarly", "devoid of any calculation or avarice", characterized by "the joy of squandering, which is the same as sacrificing, in moments of spiritual elevation".

22 Nicolae, STEINHARDT *Jurnalul fericirii*, p. 104. The condemnation of sin as a spiritual disease, the absence of a politically correct discourse, on the contrary, the manifestation of holy anger, of hatred towards sin, "contempt towards the prudent and the avaricious" as regret for the smallness of soul that dominates them.

23 Nicolae STEINHARDT, *Jurnalul fericirii*, p. 104. Nobility is a joy in itself, belonging to the race of God, even more so in the case of Christ, the Son of God by nature. One observes in Him "a sure sense of greatness," who does not do good to receive the praise or approval of flatterers.

24 Nicolae STEINHARDT, *Jurnalul fericirii*, p. 104. Detachment, in the sense of purity that cannot be corrupted or constrained by evil.

All these features reflect the mystery of the coexistence of justice and love, without canceling any of them, under the guidance of sacrificial nobility. Only the one capable of self-sacrifice for the good of his neighbor or out of love for God is truly the bearer of spiritual nobility.

In the earthly life of the Savior Jesus Christ, reproduced in the Holy Gospels and reiterated throughout the New Testament after Pentecost, through His extended Body – the Church –, humanity is offered a true foretaste of the presence of Emmanuel (“God with us”), prophesied by the prophets. They are sprinkled, with an intensity never seen before, with memorable examples of nobility, in which the divine is mirrored in the human. These become a leitmotif of the feeling of the Kingdom of God in our midst. (*Luke 17, 21*) Whether it is the Person of God the Father, Who “so loved the world that He gave His only begotten Son, that whoever believes in Him should not perish but have eternal life” (*John 3, 16*), whether it is the Person of the incarnate Son of God, Who, nailed to the Holy Cross, longs for our transfiguration: “Father, forgive them, for they know not what they do” (*Luke 23, 34*), whether it is the Person of the Holy Spirit, the Comforter par excellence, Who “prays for us with groanings unutterable” (*Romans 8, 26*), or the nobility of some exponents of humanity – the Virgin Mary, Joseph and Nicodemus, the myrrh-bearing women, the Holy Apostle Paul – all these examples of spiritual nobility constitute a call to rediscover the beauty of this virtues often disregarded.

The beauty of nobility is like the divine light that warms and liberates the prison of the soul immersed in the darkness of disorder and despair. It amazes with its unearthly nature, contrary to the wisdom of this age (*1 Corinthians 2, 6*), cunning and mercantile. It seems detached from a fairy-tale world, with beautiful faces who risk themselves to restore the luminaries in heaven.²⁵ A noble soul, says Saint Paisios the Athonite, has claims only from itself, sacrifices itself for others without expecting reward, forgets everything it offers, but remembers even the smallest thing received. It has generosity, humility, simplicity, disinterest, honesty – it has them all.²⁶ In the face of spiritual nobility, eyes blinded by the brilliance of silver remain incomprehensible, bewildered by this waste of energy and trust (*Matthew 26, 9*).

25 Nobility rekindles or intensifies in those around us the feeble light of dormant consciousness.

26 Sfântul PAISIE AGHIORITUL, „Patimi și virtuți”, p. 246.

Nobility is communal; it is shared disarmingly, in a Christlike way, uniting in the offering of oneself the one who receives with the one who gives himself, after the model of Christ. The expectations of a noble man are atypical in their simplicity, naturalness and hierarchy. His boundless trust in God's care and in the eternal value of the divine commandments is his best support, and living them gives him "the greatest joy and spiritual cheerfulness."²⁷ This silent but authentic joy becomes fuel for new gestures of nobility, shaping the entire being in the image of the All-Good and having in itself "a radiant force."²⁸ Although the world often presents itself as evil, unjust, vile, and "only negative signals come from everywhere"²⁹ which recommends barricading oneself under the umbrella of cowardice and the instinct of preservation, nobility remains altruistic, responsible, and often heroic. Without being spectacular, without making a fuss, nobility works miracles, saves souls and lives otherwise doomed to degradation, destruction, humiliation. A noble soul proves that it has been conquered by divine nobility, by the greatness of God. One cannot be a true Christian if one has not been caught "in the net of Christ"³⁰, for nobility is the seal that certifies the indwelling of the Holy Spirit in the human heart. Where there is nobility, "there Christ rests and there is the blessing of Christ".

Nobility is cultivated through spiritual sensitivity, through imitation of the martyrs who rejoiced more to suffer for God than to be liberated by human interventions or imperial edicts. In them, human justice and logic did not work – "because nobility is outside of logic"³¹ – but spiritual justice, which functions according to heavenly laws. These remind man of the dignity of his calling, of the eternal significance of every thought, word, or gesture, and put him back on the path of following Christ the Crucified, at first steep, culminating in Golgotha, but then flooded with the imperishable light of the Resurrection and eternal life. "He who receives injustice receives into his heart Christ the unjust. In their depths, injustices bring forth benefits. No one can wrong us when

27 Sfântul PAISIE AGHIORITUL, „Patimi și virtuți”, p. 246.

28 Sfântul DUMITRU STĂNILOAE, nota 698 la Varsanufie și Ioan, „Scrisori duhovnicești”, în col.: *Filocalia*, vol. XI, Ed. Humanitas, București, 2009, p. 402.

29 Nicolae STEINHARDT *Jurnalul fericirii*, p. 104.

30 Sfântul PAISIE AGHIORITUL, „Patimi și virtuți”, p. 245.

31 Sfântul PAISIE AGHIORITUL, „Patimi și virtuți”, p. 246.

we do not wrong ourselves. When we do not live spiritually, we wrong ourselves, and then we live spiritually when we keep the commandments.”³²

Dignity begins where you choose not to betray your values. To remain pure in mind and heart, not putting on the cloak of hypocrisy when you feel you need personal favors and avoiding using others when the decisions belong to you.

In this sense, I remembered what Mircea Eliade says. He finds it appropriate to understand the effort to achieve true moral perfection through repentance, as an authentic form of asceticism: “I wonder if true asceticism would not be renouncing the thirst for the fruits of our actions, renouncing acting as people, as individuals, but letting someone else, God, manifest through our acts. For if God must manifest Himself through creation, He chooses not always saints and prophets, but also people like us, with human sins and failings. To make your body the instrument of your God — why is this commandment not among so many others?”³³

I find the proximity between the concept of dignity and that of asceticism in Eliade justified. Dignity, in a moral sense, presupposes fidelity to values and the refusal of compromise, and the great Romanian philosopher proposes precisely a vision of asceticism as liberation from the thirst for the fruit of one’s own deeds and as a willingness to become a son of God.

An ancient saying rightly says, “Noblesse oblige!”, but not in the sense of an external constraint, but – at least in the case of spiritual nobility – from reasons of the heart, which the cold and calculating mind cannot comprehend.³⁴ In the perspective of eternity, a moment of generosity, of mercy, of sacrifice springing from a heart wounded by divine love, or from the desire to do good and serve man, is worth more than all the wealth of this world locked in the locks of stinginess and vanity.

32 Sfântul PAISIE AGHIORITUL, „Patimi și virtuți”, p. 245.

33 Mircea ELIADE, *Încercarea labirintului. Convorbiri cu Claude-Henri Rocquet*, trad. de Doina Cornea, Ed. Humanitas, București, 1990, p. 172.

34 Sfântul PAISIE AGHIORITUL, „Patimi și virtuți”, p. 246.

Conclusions

In conclusion, we consider that the Venerable Saint Paisios the Aghiorite is a promoter of a new kind of cardinal virtue in today's world, which he suggestively calls spiritual nobility. He recommends it as the purest expression of Christian love, a form of sacrificial and merciful love. Even if in modern culture nobility is assimilated or renamed in the form of volunteerism, philanthropy or heroic sacrifice, it is more than volunteerism, interested in the accumulation of professional experience, more purified of egoism than parade or purely material philanthropy and, unlike heroic sacrifice, dependent on calamities and wars - a humble sacrificial state in peacetime.

Father Paisios the Aghiorite remains a landmark in terms of communicating the Gospel to today's man, through his way of speaking being enlightening, introducing dogmatic teachings into the sphere of spirituality, of spiritual living, to help us understand them.

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